

A Delightful and Enjoyable Fable about Human Philosophy and Consciousness

Amazon Book Review Series of “Wild Wise Weird”

Piya & EdHockeyJr

United States, January 3, 2025

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A delightful journey through fables and stories!

As a student of philosophy, I always enjoy this kinda book where human philosophy and consciousness is discussed and explained with examples from our generational classic stories. Very delightful and enjoyable book. Must buy if you want to try a different taste in book.

Piya

★★★★★ **A delightful journey through fables and stories !**

Reviewed in the United States on January 3, 2025

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Helpful

Report

EdHockeyJr

★★★★☆ **Entertaining Read**

Reviewed in the United States on January 2, 2025

Verified Purchase

Engaging fables for readers of all ages. Filled with satire yet playful and imaginative. Kept me reading. Author does a great job of painting a picture filled with intrigue. Recommended

Screenshot. Review of “Wild Wise Weird” by Piya and EdHockeyJr [1,2]. Reviewed in the United States on January 2 and 3, 2024.

Entertaining Read

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(*) Note: This paper reprints of Piya’s and EdHockeyJr’s reviews [1,2] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [3]. The reprint’s title is created based on the review’s content.

References

- [1] Piya. (2025, Jan. 03). A delightful journey through fables and stories!. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R5J001893IKYF/>
- [2] EdHockeyJr. (2025, Jan. 02). Entertaining Read. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R3B9U774J9IYM4/>
- [3] Vuong, Q. H. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6/>